

Managing Challenges Faced By South African Higher Education Institutions In Implementing Pre-Service Teacher Education Curricular

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 23, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: July 25, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Curriculum, Curriculum Design, Curriculum Implementation, Pre-Service Teacher Education, Academic Staff.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6908272</p>	<p><i>This study was informed by the persistent challenges faced by South African higher education institutions in implementing pre-service teachers' programmes. Briefly, objectives of the study were to (a) identify the challenges faced by South African higher education institutions in the curriculum implementation for pre-service teachers' preparations; (b) find out how the South African higher education institutions address the challenges they face in implementing the curriculum for pre-service teachers' preparations; and (c) investigate the views of academic staff on continuous curriculum review for pre-service teachers' preparation. Interpretive paradigm was well suited to the study that used a qualitative approach and case study method. Purposive sampling was also used to select Sixteen (16) academics as participants to this study. In-depth interviews were instruments in data collection. Through constructivist learning and experiential learning as theoretical framework, lack of contemporary material and equipment were noted while the rapid evolution of technology and lack of technical support were identified as findings of the study. Weak internet access, staff shortages, inadequate mentoring of pre-service teachers during teaching practice; were among the chief findings of the study.</i></p> <p><i>Originality/value: This is the only study that proposes the strategies that may be used to manage the challenges faced by rural South African higher education institutions in implementing pre-service teacher education curricular in the northern part of one of the provinces in South Africa. Other studies that have been conducted were used only to identify challenges that hinder the curricular implementation</i></p>

Introduction

Post 1994 and the first democratic elections, the South African government had an unenviable task at hand to deal with a segregated, fragmented, authoritarian, unequal and inefficient education system (Adler & Reed, 2002, 22-23). At this stage, South Africa was left with only one option and that was to prepare teachers for basic education as all colleges of education had been shut down. Since then, prospective teachers have been trained and prepared at universities. This happened by moving teacher education into universities and universities of technology. The restructuring was guided by the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa (1996), which states that everyone has the right to further education (Republic of South Africa, 1996).

As part of continuous restructuring, the Department of Higher Education and Training (DHET) (2011) developed a policy framework on the minimum requirement for teacher education qualifications (MRTEQ). This policy was developed to replace the Norms and Standards for Educators (NSE) which had been formulated to guide and inform the design and development of the initial teacher education programmes. In 2008 the National Qualification Framework Act increased the 8 existing NQF levels into ten. The MRTEQ policy confirms the roles of a teacher only as functions to be carried out by the collective of teachers in a specific school. The restructuring of the initial teacher programmes were ushered in by the Higher Education Qualification Sub-Framework (HEQSF). Furthermore, the revised MRTEQ (2011) was initiated regulatory changes to the Higher Education Qualification Framework (HEQF) (2007). All aligned initial teacher education programmes exit at NQF level 7 (DHET, 2015a).

The Department of Higher Education and Training (DHET) (2004:1) declared that in the process of restructuring the issue of quality could not be ignored, and therefore require institutional planning and involvement.

Lange (2017, 44-45) confirms that the role of the High Education Quality Committee (HEQC) was established under the Higher Education Act 1997. This team has the responsibility of quality assurance and management of other activities that provide commitment to programmes' credibility. Moreover, in the implementation of these,

the HEQC uses different strategies which are used internationally for quality assurance such as institutional audits and accreditation of programmes.

The South African higher education system has not yet produced the expected output due to a lack in stability; it changes from one system to another before it is understood by all stakeholders (Bitzer, 2009). Schreuder (2014, ii) agrees that the South African higher education system has undergone continuous change in programmes since the inception of democracy in 1994. It shows that since then the curriculum has failed to produce what is required by the constitution of the country. The South African constitution promotes inclusivity and equality in all spheres of government.

The university pre-service teacher education programmes had been incorporated with the programmes of teaching colleges since the year of 2000. Since then the numbers of pre-service teachers enrolled in universities have increased compared to enrolment before the incorporation of colleges. The challenge of managing heavy teaching loads started (Human Sciences Research Council 2009). Moreover, DHET (2014a, 7) identifies a lack of expertise in curriculum development and teaching methodologies among academic staff and a lack of infrastructural support, learning spaces, Wi-Fi that is weak, overcrowding and the teaching of large classes where the majority of members of academic staff lack the methodology to teach, as some of the challenges in implementing a pre-service teachers' curriculum. Rural universities have worse problems as they mostly attract students from a rural background who have not been exposed to the diversity and demand of the academic environment.

The gap between basic education and higher education causes a lot of frustration for pre-service teachers. The university content is not aligned to school subject matter. However, the DHET (2014b,16) maintains that there are no other clear proposals on the table that have not already been tested to various extents. Among other things they pay attention to improving pedagogy and increasing the use of information technology including interactive teaching and learning.

The South African government uses continuous educational restructuring as a strategy for overcoming challenges that were discovered in the process of implementing previous curriculums. This is done without continuous teacher development. Currently South African universities are responsible for producing teachers who play a role in curriculum implementation. Mpfu and de Jager (2017, 203) agree that novice teachers are not always prepared to undertake the responsibilities of teaching. Researchers claim that training programmes have not effectively prepared them for the actual instructional practices. Mashau (2012) argues that pre-service teacher training is inadequate for the South African education system and focus of training is mainly only on teaching and learning.

Mabusela, Ngidi and Imenda (2016, 63) declare that studies to investigate educators' experiences in implementing curriculum since the restructuring of education systems are very limited. The problem that this study seeks to investigate stems from the fact that there is insufficient documented information on how faculties responsible for teacher education have experienced post-apartheid educational restructuring in their practice. Furthermore, changes of this nature affect all phases of education, because of reformation of institutions by removing teacher education from colleges and assigning it to universities as curriculum developers. Academics are additionally affected as role-players in the implementation of educational transformation, and there is a need to document their experiences of curriculum implementation for pre-service teachers' preparation.

The present study, titled *managing challenges faced by South African higher education institutions in implementing pre-service teacher education curricular*, through constructivist learning and experiential learning as lenses attempts to achieve the following objectives:

- Identifying of the challenges faced by South African Higher Education institutions in the curriculum implementation for pre-service teachers' preparation;
- Finding out how the South African higher education institutions address the challenges they are facing in implementing the curriculum for pre-service teachers' preparation; and
- Investigating of the views of academics on continuous curriculum review for pre-service teachers' preparation.

METHODOLOGY

The position of the study was found within the interpretivist paradigm; the reason, it had to interpret and record the challenges that are facing South African tertiary institutions in the implementation of teacher education. A qualitative research method was suitable for this study because the researcher received the data first-hand from participants. In adopting a qualitative research approach, "*the researcher seeks a deeper understanding of the views of a group or a single individual*" (Creswell,2014, 140). The prominence of a qualitative research approach was in advancing a different and special setting instead of focusing on a general setting. Therefore, the important meaning was the one that was sensitive to participants. Being sensitive revealed how participants

viewed a particular aspect of matter (Lune and Berg 2016). Through purposeful sampling, sixteen academics were identified and used as participants to the study. Participants to this study were indicated by the codes LA; LB; LC; LD; LE; LF; LG; LH; LI; LJ; LK; LL; LM; LN; LO; and LP.

The academics used were selected on their experience or number of years in the academic fraternity. Five years of experience of implementing curriculum for pre-service teachers from academics was suitable in this study to establish the required experiences that would make this study a success. According to the university's norms and standards, to implement curriculum for pre-service teachers, an academic must be in position of at least a relevant master's degree at NQF level 9. Therefore, it was found that all academics who participated in this study met the minimum requirements of implementing curriculum for pre-service teachers. Regardless of the fact that all participants met the requirement in terms of qualifications, there is persistence of challenges facing South African tertiary institutions when it comes to the implementation of a pre-service curriculum. Moreover, (88%) of participants had spent many years of experience in implementing curriculum for pre-service teachers, and only (12%) had a difference between years spent in implementing pre-service teachers' curriculum and as an academic in general. Additionally, 69% of participants had more than 10 years of experience in implementing teacher education. Qualitative Description (QD), table 2 and 3 injected in the study, which simply mean that qualitative content analysis is often supplemented by descriptive Statistic to describe the study sample. QD involves low-inference interpretation. The researcher only wanted to capture the profile of the participants as criteria to justify their selection in the study. That gives sound evidence that those academics had implemented more than two different curricula for pre-service teachers. The population used was appropriate because the study took place in the period where the old curriculum was phased out and a new curriculum was being introduced. The new curriculum is prescribed in a new policy document called *Minimum requirements for teacher education qualification* (MRTEQ) and Higher Education Qualification Sub-framework (HEQSF). In-depth interviews were used to collect data from academics who were used as participants in this study. Apart from interviews, documents were analysed to give support to the themes and categories that were formulated from collected data through interviews. This was done based on the main aim and objectives of the study. Analysing the documents was also useful to close the gaps found from the data collected through interviews.

1. Challenges faced by South African higher education institutions in the curriculum implementation for pre-service teachers' preparation

1.1 Overcrowding in lecture halls

Overcrowding in lecture halls was identified as one of the main challenges that hinders the smooth implementation of curriculum for pre-service teachers. This was revealed by all participants to this study and it was also found in the document published by the university on facts and figures on enrolment and permanent academic staff that was expected to implement curriculum for pre-service teachers. The total number of permanent academic staff in 2013 was 299; that number was expected to serve 16 591 students. In 2018, the total number of permanent academic staff was 295 and they were expected to serve 17 952 students. However, the faculty under study listed 4 934 students as pre-service teachers. A decrease in the number of permanent academics that was discovered while there was an increase in the number of students enrolled supports the concern raised by the current academics that are expected to implement pre-service teachers' curriculum (Unizulu, 2018). The following point was stated by participant to relate on the issue of overcrowding: LC: *It is very difficult to implement curriculum due to big numbers that I have in the classroom.*

1.2 Physical infrastructure and technology

Eighty-eight percent (88%) of participants identified slow development in the infrastructure as one of the concerns that hinders the appropriate implementation of a pre-service teachers' curriculum. They believe that slow development of infrastructure contributed to the problem of overcrowding of students. Basically the lecture rooms that had been used seven years ago are the same lecture rooms that are used currently, even though the number of students enrolling has drastically increased. Participant said: LA: *"I have taught in so many universities, but I have never faced this situation. Same type of lecture rooms, there is no flexibility, chairs are fixed. They are also small to fit the number of students admitted for B.Ed."*

Dania, Obro, and Owhorhu (2016) argue that tertiary institutions must employ a leadership team that knows and understands how to develop physical infrastructure at a tertiary institution. To find such individuals, the university must headhunt and consider the most relevant experiences for the situation at hand. One participant responded as follows to the question of, *"How were related problems/challenges treated at your university?"*: LD: *"They are not treated, they are ignored."*

1.3 Code switching and language barrier

Most of the pre-service teachers and learners find it difficult to comprehend content of the respective subjects due to the barrier of the language of teaching and learning. Learners also do not easily understand questions that are asked during assessment period. That may be caused either by the ambiguity of the question asked, or by a barrier to language of teaching and learning from the side of learners (Flynn&Curdt-Christiansen, 2018).

Participants were asked this question, “*Are there any challenges you have encountered that are related to teaching practice? If any, what are those challenges?*” These are some of their answers: LA: “*Code switching has been the culture to teaching for most of the student teachers. I don’t know if the language barrier is with the student teachers or learners. I have also notice that most of the lessons have been rehearsed by the student teachers with the learners. They did not display its originality.*”

1.4 Mentoring of pre-service teachers

Researchers are of the view that teachers who are expected to be mentors of pre-service teachers during teaching practice are not clear about their responsibilities. There is no memorandum of understanding between the university and schools on teaching practice that the researchers could be provided with by the university. Another question that was asked to participants was, “*Are there any challenges you have encountered that are related to teaching practice? If any, what are those challenges?*” one participant said: LC: “*Sometime when student teachers go out, you may find some of them telling you that the mentors are not giving them support and I’m not so sure whether the student educator is trying to appeal to your lenience.*”

1.5 Conditions of teaching facilities in schools

Infrastructure, furniture, technical facilities and books that are not suitable and sufficient to implement curriculum in some of the schools frustrate teaching practice for pre-service teachers (Mpolomoka et al. 2017). Apart from the fact that students are made aware of the conditions that prevail in schools, some of the conditions do not allow teaching and learning to be implemented. The researcher upholds that lack of infrastructure and other teaching facilities do not only affect the performance of pre-service teachers, but also the eagerness and intention of becoming a teacher. Physical facilities play an instrumental role in producing a good outcome. The next question asked to participants was, “*Are there any challenges you have encountered that are related to teaching practice? If any, what are those challenges?*” and participant’s answer was as follows: LK: “*Students are complaining that they are not getting materials that they supposed to be using to deliver their subject.*”

1.6 Pre-service teachers’ preparedness and behaviour

Mentors also notice negative behaviour in some of the student teachers while they have their teaching practice. Academics find it difficult to give realistic and accurate scores when they assess pre-service teachers due to poor performance of pre-service teachers in the classroom. Participant said the following in response to the question of some of the challenges that related to teaching practice: LO: “*Students lack professional discipline and commitment. Mentors have submitted that student teachers absent themselves from teaching practice after they have been assessed by the lecturers from university.*”

All pre-service teachers were supplied with journals as a guiding document for teaching practice. Documents were designed separately for each level from level 1 to level 4. B.Ed. 1 pre-service teachers were expected to visit schools for experience through observation in term three, in the second semester. First-year pre-service teachers were expected to observe their mentors on school functionality, classroom management, and teaching approaches. The faculty handbook shows that B.Ed. 1 students had their module on classroom management in the second semester when they were back from their school experience. Additionally, first-year students would be doing their pedagogical studies on curriculum development only in year two, first semester. A comparable case happened to Postgraduate Certificate in Education (PGCE) students where they had visited schools for teaching experience every Wednesday, in semester one, before they had acquired skills on educational management (UNIZULU, 2019). This also indicates that even if students were exposed to further work integrated learning (WIL), they would still find it difficult to be competent during practice teaching.

2. Views of academics on continuous curriculum review for pre-service teachers’ preparation

2.1 Views of academic staff on what informs curriculum review internally

Participants to the study did not give similar answers about what informs curriculum review internally. There were participants who indicated that they were not playing any part to influence the review of curriculum. Some of the participants revealed that they understand the process that informs the curriculum review. Among the participants, there were also those who had no clue at all about what informs curriculum review internally. The university has a policy on programme reviews that states the following: *South African higher education faces multiple stakeholder demands for greater responsiveness to societal needs and the programme accreditation system seeks to be responsive to the objectives of higher education transformation as reflected in various policy and legislative documents* (CHE, 2004). Participants said: LB: “*Department of Higher Education and Training (DHET) pronounce that curriculum need to be reviewed every after three (3) years.*” LF: “*I would think of the needs of the students, the needs also to look at our offerings, what we offer, if still relevant and think those are the things the review of curriculum should be based on them.*”

It can also indicate that participants were part of the Re-curriculation of the current MRTEQ aligned programmes but they do not have any guidelines on what informed programme review. This can imply that most academics do not read and have understanding of programme qualification Mix (PQM) of the university understudy. A participant also said this: LD: *"I'm guessing that there is a chance that our B.Ed. programme could be reviewed in 2022. I don't know how the internal process goes if there is. Nobody told me how to do that, there are no instructions for that you should be reviewing curriculum every year internal or whatever."*

2.2 Views of academic staff on why the curriculum at higher education level is under constant review

Frequent changes in curriculum needs of the society had been identified as the main reason to frequent review of curriculum at higher education level. The strength of the university in responding quickly with its PQM to socio-economic trends, challenges and opportunities, is one of the competitive advantages that puts it ahead of competitors and makes it attractive to students, sponsors and the industry. A participant expressed this view: LG: *"The main purpose of higher education is to meet the current challenges of the country. So now they keep reviewing because old programmes may be talking to old things while here we train people to go to world of work, and the world of work is the dynamic system that keeps changing all the time."*

Other reasons apart from changes of societal needs, research practices, schools' curriculum, educational trends and demand of teachers in schools had been identified as reasons to review curriculum at higher education level. Furthermore, it is stated in the CHE document that the HEQC may delegate the responsibility for reaccrediting its own programmes through a process of institutionally managed programme evaluations to the institution, and it is therefore important to have a system that is sufficiently robust to meet these needs (CHE 2004). On the question, *"Why is the curriculum at higher education institutions always reviewed?"*, participants said: LD: *"Quality assurance, trends, research practices, policy requirements."*

2.3 Approaches and views of academic staff on how reviewing of the curriculum impacts on curriculum implementation

It is never a smooth journey to implement curriculum at any level after changes. While the change may be beneficial to the society and community that the university is serving, it may not be easy for academics as the implementers of curriculum. The reality is that academics experience heavy workloads during the transition period from an old curriculum to a new curriculum. Besides challenges that are experienced during transition, the new curriculum never fills all the gaps discovered from the old curriculum (Glatthorn, Boschee, Whitehead & Boschee, 2018). Clifford and Montgomery (2015) reveal that academics have no power of decision about what is included in the content of curriculum. That alone means academics need more time to understand the new curriculum while they are implementing the same curriculum. The participants said the following: *"It always brings new knowledge and improvement. So it demands us to work hard to adapt on changes."*

Another pertinent issue raised referred to involving every member of academic staff when curriculum changes were effected. It was stated that if you were not part of the team that was doing the review, the curriculum changes were more straining to implement. Participants summarised that as follows:

LG: *"I think when we are reviewing curriculum most people must be involved in the reviewing of the curriculum."*

However, if new curriculum has to come in, it must be supported with resources to make it a success. If old resources are no longer appropriate for the new curriculum, relevant resources need to be brought in. Otherwise, it may be difficult for academics to be judged about something that is not fully supported with suitable resources. Besides, the curriculum needs to be monitored and evaluated at a later stage. Without full resources, monitoring and evaluating the course may be compromised (Romiszowski, 2016). Participants were not happy about the way transition was taking place. The curriculum structure revealed that more academics should be employed by the university across all departments. Employment of new academics has not yet happened, and that means it has been difficult for serving academics to implement the curriculum. One participant said this: LL: *"The new curriculum has started already, but this curriculum will experience problems when students get into level three because in level three the curriculum says academics must specialise."*

2.4 Preparation and strategies to curriculum review and implementation

Participants were given an opportunity to list the training sessions and workshops they had attended to prepare for curriculum review and implementation. There were those academics who were not part of the curriculum reviewing panel, but who are expected to implement curriculum and there were those academics who were part of curriculum reviewing panel and expected to implement curriculum. Moreover, the designed document may be not clear to some academics. Absence from meetings intended to be instrumental to discuss challenges is a challenge on its own. Most of the participants indicated that they had never been involved with curriculum

reviewing. This is evidence to the fact that they had never been trained or supported for curriculum review and curriculum implementation. Participants articulated this as follows:

LA: *“What training? I don’t remember any training to prepare for curriculum review. It never happened for me. I’m not sure about other academics.”* LP: *“I have never received any training that supports curriculum review. Training was not available at all.”*

The researchers’ view is that academics find themselves in a difficult position to deal with preparation for curriculum review and implementation since they are commonly allocated with other responsibilities such as administrative duties, research, teaching and community engagement. The shortage in human resources is one of the major factors that subject academics to difficult conditions. While workshops and training may occur as frequently as possible if there are weak or slow students that remain behind when the old curriculum is phased out, the developed strategy may not work.

2.5 Present state of pre-service teachers’ curriculum at the university

According to Pillay (2019), the tools used to evaluate the curriculum in place must be accessed and clear to all academics who are responsible for curriculum implementation. However, if academics are not aware of the criteria and standards for curriculum accreditation, they might not be aware of the present state of curriculum that is implemented by the faculty under study. All participants that were part of the study confirmed that their understanding of the present state of pre-service teachers’ curriculum at their university. The question that was asked to participants was, *“What is the present state regarding curriculum review at your university?”* Participants’ answers were as follows: LH: *“I know that are programmes have been approved at least by DHET and SAQA. I also know that it was a long and intense journey for those who participated in the programme.”* LI: *“We have reviewed undergraduate programmes and we sent them to DHET, two were fully accredited and we are implementing them. The PGCE one was also approved and accredited.”*

2.6 Guiding documents used for curriculum review and implementation

Currently there is a national document that provides guidelines on minimum requirement for teachers’ qualifications, commonly known as MRTEQ. Most of the participants were aware of the MRTEQ document which provides guidelines and procedure when re-curriculating a programme in teacher education. The document provides guidelines, distribution of the credit to knowledge mix, including the number of weeks for work integrated learning (DHET 2015b). Participants provided different answers as follows: LA: *“We have document called MRTEQ. I think that was the document they have used on Re-curriculation.”* LF: *“At the moment I think the document called MRTEQ, they are trying to state clearly what the minimum requirements for initial teacher education are, the CAPS documents and those are policy documents that one could use.”*

Guidelines for implementing a curriculum that has been recently reviewed are listed in the faculty handbook as the purpose of a module; description and code of the module; content that should be covered in a particular module; types of assessment to be done in a module, and the methodology that should be used to facilitate the module. The assessment marks for each module are stated very clearly. However, the resources and materials that should be used to implement the curriculum were not stated and the distribution of content and allocation of time in which content should be covered were not mentioned in the handbook (UNIZULU, 2019).

2.9 Approaches and views of academic staff on how to overcome challenges encountered in implementing curriculum

Exclusion of stakeholders when there are changes in curriculum was stated as one of the things that can be corrected to overcome the challenges of implementing curriculum. Beside exclusion of stakeholders, frequent review of curriculum was also mentioned as a cause of challenges in curriculum implementation. The following are remarks from the participants: LB: *“Stakeholders must be involved and feedback be given to relevant personnel. Curriculum should be at least for the period of 10 years to allow teachers to master it.”* LC: *“I think I will suggest that there always should be constant feedback from school principals of what they are seeing on our product whether they are performing well or not and even pointing out areas where they think should be enhanced by the university”*

Apart from stakeholders that are side-lined when the curriculum is implemented, short staffing was pinpointed as one of the hindrances for the smooth implementation of curriculum. Ajisafe, Orifa and Balogun (2015) posit that staff members who are not stressed by work overload produce the best quality results. The volume of work that is expected to be performed by workers has a direct influence on the performance of an organisation as a whole. Similarly, McCowan (2018) identifies the shortage of staff as one of the barriers in Kenyan universities. Suitable infrastructure and other technical resources also remain as challenges that are hard to deal with, and they compromise the effectiveness of curriculum implementation of pre-service teachers (SchererTondeur,

Siddiq&Baran, et al.2018).The question asked to participants was, “Do you have any suggestions to deal with the challenges encountered in implementing curriculum in general?” Participants’ answers were as follows: LD: “Staffing. University must employ more staff. Understaffing compromises quality.”LH: “Better technology, venues which are flexible not with these mounted desks where people cannot move, can we have other ways to have academic resources online to avoid printing, can we have human resources.”

Apart from the shortage of staff, suitable infrastructure and other technical facilities, the unavailability of formal training and mentoring of new academics were seen as some of the most pressing concerns to the journey of academics. Cleary, Jackson, Sayers and Lopez (2017) state that mentoring of new academics is one of the most significant steps that tertiary institutions can initiate. However, if there is shortage of academics in the institution, that important step may remain only a dream to accomplish. To assign the task of mentoring to academics requires a pool of academics to choose from, due to the fact that academics have many responsibilities to fulfil. Abugre and Kpinpuo (2017) maintain that universities in developing countries are still behind in implementing a strategy for mentoring young academics.Participants were asked to suggest how to overcome the phenomenon, and one responded as follows:LF: “I would think that new staff should be properly inducted. Unlike what happened to us, it is different environment that you just thrown to it and nobody mentors you. I think it is important to have mentors and people who can introduce you to the culture of university.”

2.10 Approaches and views of academic staff on continuous review of curriculum for the future

The issue of involving stakeholders from the beginning was mentioned as something that could not be ignored when changes in the curriculum were still to be done. Stakeholders must be involved in the entire process, from the beginning up to the end of the process when a trained teacher is employed. Although there are different factors that cause influence the frequency of the curriculum review, relevant stakeholders must be part of the process. Moreover, a community based review process is suggested (Vangrieken et al. 2017). Gillgren et al. (2019) aver that an integral part of curriculum review is consultation with all stakeholders. Consultation must not exclude academics or students as they are directly involved with the implementation stage.Participants addressed that as follows:LB: “We need to invite more people to come on board from the beginning to the final stage.” LH: “I think we need more community members to come in to curriculum review processes such as business people, so that they can talk to what is relevant for their context. For me I wish that students themselves could be there, schools should be there in the process to understand it from this point going forward.”

Involvement of DHET officials from the beginning of the process of reviewing and Re-curriculation has been indicated as the preferential manner to conduct continuous review of the curriculum. The DHET provides support by guiding universities on corrections that should be made. Participants stated further that: LI: “Although as faculty we identify people from other institution to come and advice, but I have the feeling that even the DHET officials should come on board so that whatever we do and prepare as we review curriculum they give proper guidance. Not that they wait until we submit and they reject or they accept.”

From the above statement it is clear that some academics do not understand the processes of programme accreditation, from the internal structure at university level and the external body that reviews programme according to the requirements as stated by DHET, HEQC and SAQA as the quality assurance body for accreditation. Guidelines to review the curriculum should be there to guide the process, not to influence the process to a particular position. Academics of the institution must be given the freedom to come up with something that would be appropriate for their students. One participant answered as follows: LL: “I would say, the university is an institution of higher learning. They must sit down and draft policies on basis of experience they have in the teacher education field. It must not be something that come from up there, but everybody must be involved at university. It much better if it is done by the lecturers.”

New trends and educational issues are asserted as major factors of continuous curriculum review at any institution of higher learning. South Africa as one of the developing countries in Africa has engaged itself in different ways in transforming the education system as a whole. Current trends show that many of the developing countries are moving towards using technological tools in research and teaching (Olelewe&Okwor 2017). Participants stated this: LN: “I think the curriculum it should be continuously reviewed, because if it is not reviewed you cannot get to expose you students to the latest trends in education.”

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

1. Identifying challenges faced by South African Higher Education institutions in the curriculum implementation for pre-service teachers' preparation

The findings revealed numerous and persistent challenges that hinder pre-service teachers' curriculum implementation for South African higher education institutions. Overcrowding in lecture halls is one of the challenges that has stayed unresolved for many years. Overcrowding prevents academics from using different strategies for teaching. Shortage of suitable lecture halls for foundation phase students disturbs clear planning of implementing curriculum aligned to expectations. Poor technology and technical support as additional impending challenges. Wi-Fi and internet hotspots that are frequently weak for sustained internet access have been commonly experienced by academics and pre-service teachers. Other technological tools that are found in lecture halls are not always in a working condition, and in many cases are found broken. There is a shortage in staffing or human resources. English as language of instruction affects the confidence of many of the pre-service teachers during teaching practice period. Meetings between mentor teachers and academics to discuss the mentoring of pre-service teachers are non-existent. Additionally, resources and materials that pre-service teachers have been taught in theory are not available at their chosen schools for teaching practice. Pre-service teachers find it difficult to adapt in those conditions. Unruly behaviour and unpreparedness due to that B.Ed. 1 and Post Graduate Certificate in Education students attend their school experience without understanding classroom management and pedagogical concepts related to curriculum development.

2. Investigating the approaches and views of academic staff on continuous curriculum review for pre-service teachers' preparation

Findings of the study showed that academics are aware of principles and procedures that internally inform curriculum review. Societal needs and demands that regularly change can also influence the review of the curriculum. Moreover, it was found that when curriculum review is done, not all academics are brought on board to be part of curriculum reviewing. Additionally, findings revealed that the way the new curriculum is structured requires more staff for a smooth implementation. Strangleman (2017) claims that even if changes bring better ways of operating at any organisation, it takes time for employees to accept changes. It is also common for people who have been in a particular institution for so long to resist any or all changes, even if it is clearly change for the better. Findings revealed that no clear strategy was employed, nor formal training ever organised for academics before curriculum review is performed. De Vries and Korotov (2016) suggest that any organisation implementing changes should offer training and workshops. Policy document called MRTEQ was used to review new curriculum. Policy document used was provided by the DHET and was applicable to all other universities. Nel and Adam (2014) emphasise the importance of following a certain route when curriculum review is done. The findings confirmed that all stakeholders must be consulted and involved for them to understand the curriculum being implemented. It was also found that the curriculum specialist that is normally sent by the DHET must be involved from the very beginning of the curriculum review process rather than at a more advanced stage.

CONCLUSION

The study's major findings on aspects that need special attention are as follows: Shortage of staff; overcrowding; inappropriate planning; lack of technological tools; lack of participation; shortage of physical infrastructure; lack of reliable internet access; and lastly, challenges relating specifically to teaching practice itself. Alongside, findings of the study revealed that constructivist learning and experiential learning theories are not only framework of this study, but they also give framework to curriculum designers on what kind of curriculum should be designed for pre-service teachers. The study findings also showed that both theories are pertinent when designed curriculum is being implemented. They give different strategies that can be used to implement curriculum. Academics should guide students while they play a major role of their learning, and that can be based on constructivist learning theory. On the other hand findings showed that using of experiential learning theory while establishing learning experiences of students cannot be ignored. Concisely, findings discovered that integration of experiential learning theory and constructivist theory is imperative for pre-service teachers' preparations.

RECOMMENDATIONS

This study intended to investigate how challenges faced by South African higher education institutions in implementing teacher education for pre-service teachers are managed supported by a constructivist learning theory and experiential learning theory as theoretical framework. The recommendations proposed are as follows:

- ✓ A resource centre that is able to support a large number of pre-service teachers must be considered by the university.

- ✓ Security personnel must be allocated for each lecture hall to protect physical infrastructure and other digital tools in lecture halls. Moreover, a campaign against vandalism must be launched to involve all parties that use the university's infrastructure.
- ✓ A strong Wi-Fi network must be made available in all lecture halls. This may allow pre-service teachers to access the internet and material on Moodle while a lecturer is presenting. Data screens should be placed at convenient intervals along the walls of the lecture hall for students to see what is projected by a lecturer while the lecture is in progress.
- ✓ Mentor teachers must be trained by academics to prepare them for the teaching practice of pre-service teachers. Universities need to have Memoranda of Understanding (MoU's) with the DBE in support of the university in training teachers as mentors that will also provide guidelines for mentoring the pre-service teachers.
- ✓ Channels of communication between university and schools where pre-service teachers do their teaching practice must be improved. At present, pre-service teachers are aware that there is no communication between university and mentor teachers; that is why unruly behaviour of students is experienced.
- ✓ More than one university must be used for benchmarking, in order to collect more information that would assist the faculty to be on par with other institutions.
- ✓ The representative from DHET must be part of curriculum review at the beginning of the review process. That may assist to close loopholes as early as possible, rather than raising concerns at the later stage of curriculum review.
- ✓ A teaching and learning committee must periodically collect trends and societal needs and feedback from basic education about pre-service teachers that had been produced by the faculty under study. This may assist the university to know about their graduate teachers for future preparation.

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